

FORMS AND TYPES OF TRAINING ORGANIZATION

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Abstract. This article separately shows the forms of training, types and structure of lessons, non-standard lessons and auxiliary forms of training. The form part of the lesson shows various types of lessons and methods for effectively using teaching aids.

Keywords: Forms of training, Didactic (educational), Problem-based learning, Programmed training, Distance learning.

ФОРМЫ И ВИДЫ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ПОДГОТОВКИ

Аннотация. В данной статье отдельно показаны формы обучения, виды и структура уроков, нестандартные уроки и вспомогательные формы обучения. В формальной части урока показаны различные виды уроков и методы эффективного использования учебных пособий.

Ключевые слова: Формы обучения, Дидактическое (образовательное), Проблемное обучение, Программированное обучение, Дистанционное обучение.

Forms of training. Didactic (educational) systems do not become a thing of the past without leaving a trace. They are being transformed into more progressive ones and in tune with the requirements of the time.

The main types and types of pedagogical systems: archaic (primitive); ancient (Sumerian, Egyptian, Chinese - III millennium BC); Avestan "Avesta" (Bactria, Sogd, Khorezm - 7th - 6th centuries BC); Greek (Hellenic, Roman-Greek, Roman - VI - I centuries BC); medieval (dogmatic, scholastic - V -X VI centuries AD).

Modern types of teaching: explanatory and illustrative (from the 17th century to the present). The main methods are *explanation combined with clarity*. The leading activities are *listening and memorizing*. The main requirement is *error-free reproduction of what has been learned*. The main criterion for effectiveness is *error-free reproduction of the material based on the standard answer*.

Problem-based learning. Organization of learning - *through independent acquisition of knowledge in the process of solving educational problems, development of creative thinking and cognitive activity of students*. Technology is *the creation of a problem situation and its subsequent*

solution. The advantages of problem-based learning: independent acquisition of knowledge through one's own creative activity, high interest in educational work, development of productive thinking, lasting and effective learning results. Disadvantages: poor controllability of students' cognitive activity, large amounts of time spent posing and solving problems.

Programmed training. The main goal is *to improve the management of the educational process.* Advantages of programmed training: obtaining complete and constant information about the degree and quality of mastery of the entire curriculum; the pace of learning corresponds to the individual capabilities of the student, since each student works in a mode convenient for him; saving teacher time on the process of transmitting information; the amount of time for constant monitoring of the process and result of information transfer increases. Cons: Excessive use of students' memory.

Computer training. Directions for using computers: *improving academic performance in individual academic subjects; development of general cognitive (cognitive) abilities.*

Progress in the development of personal computers (PCs) has brought teachers to the new technology of computerized (computerized) education. Programmed and computer-based learning is based on the selection of learning algorithms. Before creating a training program, you need to develop an algorithm for performing mental actions and educational operations, according to which the computer will control the scientific process.

Innovative training (innovation). Characteristic features: 1) *training in foresight, i.e. a person's orientation is not towards past experience and the present, but towards the distant future;* 2) *the student's involvement in cooperation and participation in the process of making important decisions at different levels (from local to global).*

*Distance learning (from lat. *disstata* - distance).* The goal is the opportunity to study the program of any college (university) at a distance without interruption from the main activity. Distance learning provides students with flexibility in choosing the place and time of study, learning without interruption from work. Opportunities: modern information technologies: electronic textbooks, videotapes, classes conducted through computer telecommunications, radio, TV, etc.; the opportunity to communicate with prominent scientists, scientists, cultural figures, etc.

The history and practice of teaching knows a wide variety of forms of organizing training. Each new historical stage in the development of society leaves its mark on the organization of education.

The set of forms, united on the basis of the connection between students and teachers through educational material and complementing each other, constitutes the organizational system of education (Academician of the Russian Academy of Education V.I. Slavenin).

Forms of training: individual, individual-group, collective, class-lesson, lecture-seminar and extracurricular, extracurricular, school and extracurricular.

Individual form of training. From primitive society to the 19th century; Currently - tutoring. Pros: allows you to completely individualize the content, methods and pace of the student's educational activities, and make timely adjustments to the student's activities. Leads to high results. Disadvantages: not time-efficient, limited influence of the teacher: the teacher gives the task and checks its completion; limited collaboration with other students; lack of ability to work in a team. Examples of individual training: Ibn Sina (10th century) was educated by a private teacher, Abu Abdullah an-Natili, the most prominent scientist of Bukhara. He taught him logic, philosophy, mathematics and fiqh (Muslim jurisprudence). Abu Reyhan Biruni (10th century) - was educated in the house of Abu Nasr Ibn Iraq, a famous historian and cousin of the Khorezm Shah of the Iraklid dynasty. Mastered a range of subjects that form the basis of traditional Muslim education: the Koran, Arabic language and grammar, adab (ethics), rhetoric, logic, philosophy, history, astronomy, mathematics, fiqh and a manual of fiqh (law) - a collection of Hadith "As-Sahih" al-Bukhari. An Arab gardener for Ibn Iraq (a Greek scientist-doctor) taught him Greek and Latin, botany and pharmacology.

Individual-group form. In Central Asia during the era of Avestan society (7th - 6th centuries BC): collective reading of the text, group repetition of what was read, exercises on tablets, mental training in the form of a collective conversation between the teacher and students. Maverannahr (IV - XV centuries - Mirzo Ulugbek, along with individual madrassas, introduced the form of "jamo'a" (team), close to the class-lesson system. Lecture - to a large group of shogirds (students), and practical classes in a small group). In Europe - from the 16th century.

Classroom form. For the first time in fraternal schools of Western Russia (west of modern Belarus and Ukraine) - XVII century. theoretically substantiated by Ya.A. Komensky. Its essence: students of the same age and level of development form a class that is constant for the entire period of study; the class works according to a single plan and program according to a permanent schedule; the basic unit of classes is the lesson; the lesson is dedicated to one subject; The work in the lesson is led by the teacher. Y.A. Komensky gave recommendations on how to structure the lesson. The lesson should have a BEGINNING - restoration of what was covered earlier, CONTINUATION - new material, and an END - consolidation of what was heard and completion of exercises. J. A. Komensky in "The Great Didactics" (17th century) introduced into pedagogy such concepts as "school year", "school day", "lesson", "break between classes", "school holidays".

Currently, the classroom-lesson system has undergone significant modification and modernization, but in schools around the world it is the predominant form of education, despite the fact that it is more than 350 years old. Class-lesson system. Pros: clear organizational structure; simple management of the educational process; interaction of children in the process of collective discussion of problems; emotional impact of the teacher's personality on students; cost-effectiveness of training - working with a large group. Disadvantages: targeting the average student creates difficulties for the weak and delays the development of the strong; difficulties in taking into account the individual characteristics of students, etc. At the end of the 19th century. The class-lesson form of teaching began to be criticized due to dogmatism and scholasticism in teaching and low quality of teaching. The first attempt to modernize the classroom-based form of education was made at the end of the 18th – beginning of the 19th centuries. English priest A. Bell (India) and teacher J. Lancaster (England). The impetus for this was the transition from manufacture to large-scale machine industry, which required a large number of workers with at least basic literacy.

Bell-Lancaster system of mutual education (A. Bell (India) and J. Lancaster (England) late XVIII - early XIX centuries). The essence: older students, under the guidance of a teacher, studied the material themselves, and then, having received instructions, taught those who knew less. Simultaneous coverage of more than 300 students. At the end of the 19th – beginning of the 20th centuries. The issue of individualizing the education of students with differences in their mental development becomes especially relevant. Forms of selective education appear: the Bath system (USA) and the Mannheim system (Germany).

Bata system. (Batavia-plan) USA, Batavia 1898 г.). The essence: in the class, the “main” teacher led frontal work in the lesson; assistant – individual lessons with individual students after school. Mannheim system (Mannheim, Germany, early 20th century). The essence: the distribution of students depending on abilities and performance in classes into strong, average and weak. The selection was based on observations and examinations. If successful, transfer to the strong class. But the system did not allow the weak to reach a high level.

Dalton plan (“laboratory plan”) (USA, Dalton, 1905 г.). The gist: students were not bonded over shared class work; freedom in choosing classes, the order of studying subjects. The annual volume of educational material was divided into monthly “contracts”, which were divided into daily tasks. The student entered into a “contract” with the teacher to independently study the educational material. The division by class was abolished (students worked in laboratories, the teacher did not conduct general class work, and provided consultations separately). Pros: adapt the pace of learning to the capabilities of students, develop independence and initiative, search for

rational methods of work. Disadvantages: did not contribute to the systematic mastery of the knowledge system, fragmentation, did not cover the entire volume of educational information on the subject; generated unhealthy rivalry among students.

Brigade-laboratory teaching method (20s of the twentieth century, Soviet school). The essence: the class is divided into teams (4-5 students). The teacher did not teach classes, he advised. The foreman actually reported for the task . The test was given to the entire brigade. The level of knowledge is low. IN 1936 r. this method was abolished and a classroom-based teaching system under the guidance of a teacher was recommended.

Trump's plan (Prof. L. Trump, USA, 20th century, 60s). The essence: a combination of theoretical classes in large classrooms (100-150 people) with classes in groups of 10-15 people and individual work by students. General lectures using TSO - 40% of the teaching time, work in small groups (seminars) - 20% and individual independent work - 40%.

Training team (team teaching) (USA, 70s of the twentieth century; Sweden, etc.). The essence: training is conducted by a group (team) of teachers. A qualified teacher in front of classes - parallels with a lecture, a new topic. Consolidation with teachers who conduct training sessions in classes (groups). "Ungraded school" (ungraded school). Studying at an individual pace: one subject for 5th grade, the other for 3rd grade. "Open Schools" ("Schools without walls") (USA, England). Studying in centers with libraries, in large halls with sliding walls. Training under "contract, agreement" (France, Japan). A student signs a "contract" with an "excellent" rating, where there are 19 tasks, but he completed 12 tasks with a "good" rating and receives an "unsatisfactory" rating. Must be responsible for your choices.

2. Types and structure of the lesson.

A lesson is an organizational form of teaching in which the teacher directs the collective cognitive activity of students in the class, taking into account the characteristics of each, uses tools and methods of work that create conditions for everyone to master the basics of the subject being studied during the lesson.

Each lesson consists of certain elements (links, stages), which are characterized by different types of activity of the teacher and students. The variety of lesson structures implies a variety of their types. There is no generally accepted classification of lessons in modern didactics.

Lesson typology: 1. Combined (mixed). 2. Lessons in learning new knowledge. 3. Lessons in developing new skills. 4. Lessons in generalizing and systematizing what has been learned. 5. Lessons on control and correction of knowledge and skills. 6. Lessons in the practical application of knowledge and skills.

Structure of a combined lesson (stages): updating the experience and basic knowledge of students (repetition, restoration); motivation of educational activities; message of the topic, purpose, objectives of the lesson; perception of new educational material; comprehension of educational material; generalization and systematization of knowledge; summing up the lesson; homework assignment.

Each lesson is aimed at achieving a triune goal: *to teach, educate, develop*. Taking this into account, the general requirements for the lesson are specified in didactic, educational and developmental requirements.

Didactic (educational) requirements for the lesson: clear definition of educational objectives; rationalization of the information content of the lesson (educational material); introduction of the latest technologies of cognitive activity; rational combination of various types, forms and methods of teaching; combination of collective activities with independent activities of students; providing prompt feedback for effective control and management.

Educational requirements for the lesson: determining the educational capabilities of the educational material; setting realistically achievable educational goals; educating students on universal human values; formation of vital qualities: perseverance, accuracy, responsibility, diligence, independence, efficiency, honesty, collectivism, etc.

Developmental requirements for the lesson: the formation of positive motives for educational and cognitive activity, interests, creative initiative and activity in students; conducting classes at an “advanced” level; stimulating the onset of new qualitative changes in the development of students, etc.

The formula for lesson effectiveness consists of two parts: careful preparation and mastery of delivery. A poorly planned, ill-thought-out, hastily designed lesson cannot be of high quality. Preparation of a lesson is the development of a set of measures that, under specific conditions, ensures the highest final result.

Preparing a teacher for a lesson (stages): diagnostics: “clarification” of all the circumstances of the lesson: the students’ capabilities; requests and inclinations, interests; required level of training; the nature of the educational material, the structure of the lesson; analysis of all time spent on repetition; assimilation of new information; consolidation, control and correction of knowledge. The stage ends with receiving a diagnostic card; forecasting - assessment of various options for the future lesson; design (planning) is a program for managing the educational process. A short and specific document that records important points: who to ask and when, how to start a new topic, how to reinforce it, etc.

Auxiliary forms of education: clubs, workshops, seminars, conferences, consultations, electives, educational excursions, homework for students, etc.

Lyceums and colleges use a lecture-practical teaching system. Lessons in the form of 2 lessons – 90 (80) minutes. A lecture is a form of transmitting a large amount of systematized information as an indicative basis for students' independent work. A practical lesson is a form of organization of detailing, analysis, expansion, deepening, consolidation, application and control over the assimilation of received educational information under the guidance of a teacher.

3. Non-standard lessons.

Non-traditional (non-standard) lessons: dialogue lessons, discussion, press conference lesson, didactic games, trainings, KVN-type lessons, auction lessons, lessons in museums, "Investigation is conducted by experts" lessons, "Field of Miracles" game lessons and etc.

1. Auxiliary forms of training.

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